

70 MW-Level Picosecond Mid-Infrared Radiation Generation by Difference Frequency Generation in AgGaS_2 , BaGa_4Se_7 , LiGaSe_2 , and LiGaS_2

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Abstract—Comparative study of nonlinear crystals for picosecond difference frequency generation in mid-IR is presented. Nonlinear crystals of AgGaS_2 , BaGa_4Se_7 , LiGaSe_2 , and LiGaS_2 were studied. In order to investigate the dependence of efficiency on the crystal length, three sets of crystals with lengths of 2, 4, or 8 mm were tested. The developed tunable DFG system was driven by the 1.03 μm , 1.8 ps, Yb:YAG thin-disk laser system operated at the repetition rate of 10 or 100 Hz. As the best result, picosecond mid-IR pulses at a wavelength of $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ with the energy up to 130 μJ corresponding to the peak power of $\sim 72 \text{ MW}$ were generated using the 8 mm long LiGaS_2 crystal. Using the BaGa_4Se_7 crystal, DFG tunability in the wavelength range from 6 up to 13 μm was achieved.

Index Terms—Difference frequency generation, mid-infrared radiation, nonlinear optics, picosecond lasers.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOURCES of coherent radiation in a mid-infrared (IR) spectral range ($\sim 3\text{--}20 \mu\text{m}$) are interesting for many possible applications in vibrational spectroscopy, medicine (soft tissue ablation), biology (interaction with tissue or analysis), high-harmonic generation, attosecond science, atmospheric studies, etc. [1], [2]. Laser radiation around $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ can be generated by well-developed Er^{3+} -doped lasers. Laser-diode pumped, quasi-continuous wave (QCW) lasers with $>50 \text{ W}$ of average output power are commercially available. Several works are also devoted to a development of Er^{3+} :ZBLAN fiber lasers in continuous wave (CW) or Q-switched regime [3], [4]. Nevertheless, not all temporal regimes are readily available and mainly stable mode-locked operation for ultrashort pulse generation is still challenging.

Going farther into the infrared region, laser radiation can be generated directly by some special solid-state lasers based

on Fe^{2+} or Dy^{3+} active ions. Lasers based on Dy^{3+} : PbGa_2S_4 can generate radiation at narrow spectral lines around 4.3 or 5.4 μm [5]. Fe^{2+} -based lasers can provide generally continuously-tunable radiation in a wide spectral range because of strong interaction of the electronic states with lattice vibrations. Pumping of such lasers is generally not trivial because the Fe^{2+} absorption band is located around 3 μm . Moreover, upper-state level lifetime at room temperature is in the order of hundreds of nanoseconds indicating special requirements on pumping sources. Therefore, Er^{3+} -based lasers, usually operated in a Q-switched regime, are usually used as pumping sources of Fe^{2+} -based lasers. Host materials such as ZnSe or ZnS were studied extensively and the tuning range of ~ 3.7 to 5.3 μm was presented [6], [7]. It has to be noted that the Fe^{2+} lifetime as well as fluorescence spectra and resulting tunability range are strongly influenced by the active material temperature. The spectral tuning range can be extended using other Fe^{2+} host materials such as CdTe or $\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{Te}$ and pumping of such lasers by other Fe^{2+} :ZnSe lasers [8]. For example, smooth tunability of a Fe^{2+} :CdTe laser in the range ~ 4.5 to 6.8 μm was demonstrated [9]. Concerning other temporal regimes, CW Fe^{2+} :ZnSe laser generation was achieved and mode-locked regime in the sub-picosecond time domain was also successfully reported [10]. Some of these lasers became commercially available recently.

Moreover, there are commercially available and highly developed gas lasers based on CO or CO_2 generating within the wavelength ranges of 5.2–6.0 μm or 9.1–10.9 μm , respectively. These lasers can be operated in various temporal regimes from CW to ultrashort pulse generation [11], [12]. Free-electron lasers represent another type of very versatile and broadly-tunable mid-IR radiation sources, but they suffer from complexity and costs [13]. These devices generate in a unique temporal regime. The generated macropulse with a duration of several μs consists of a $\sim\text{GHz}$ train of micropulses with $\sim 1 \text{ ps}$ duration. Semiconductor (quantum cascade) lasers present other interesting and applicable alternatives with CW output power at a level of several Watts [14], [15]. Generation of low average power sub-picosecond pulses was also presented recently [16]. There are also other alternative approaches for generation in mid-IR, for example, hydrogen Raman lasers [17].

An extensive group of applicable and highly versatile sources is based on nonlinear optical parametric processes. This concept

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has a great advantage in possibility of output wavelength tunability in a wide range given by the phase-matching conditions. There are generally several approaches: optical parametric generation (OPG), optical parametric amplification (OPA), optical parametric oscillation (OPO), and difference frequency generation (DFG) that can be considered as a special type of OPA. These individual methods are commonly combined in some multi-stage systems (OPG+OPA, OPG+DFG etc.) enabling the generation of longer wavelengths or higher energies. While OPG, OPA, and DFG can be essentially considered as single pass, OPO systems are based on multi-pass round-trip inside an optical resonator. Therefore, quality of an output beam generated by OPOs is generally better, usually close to a fundamental mode, and also the operation threshold is lower. In contrast to OPG or OPA systems, peak powers and energies generated by OPOs are orders of magnitude smaller.

DFG process, also known as parametric down-conversion, allows conversion of high-energy, visible or near-IR laser radiation into a mid-IR region or even further to THz frequency band [1], [18], [19], [20]. Concerning more closely on mid-IR region, this concept has been proven in a wide temporal range from CW [21] to pulsed regime with pulse duration from nanoseconds down to femtoseconds [22]. As DFG is a three-wave mixing nonlinear process, the nonlinear crystals have to be non-centrosymmetric, i.e. present the second order nonlinearity $\chi^{(2)}$. A choice of the nonlinear crystal depends on several factors and the desired wavelength belongs to the most important. Oxide crystals, as for example BBO (BaB_2O_4), KTP (KTiOPO_4), or LiNbO_3 are widely used. Moreover, many of these crystals can be periodically-poled in order to increase conversion efficiency. On the other hand, their transparency range is limited, i.e. up to $\sim 2.9\ \mu\text{m}$ in the case of BBO, up to $\sim 4.3\ \mu\text{m}$ for KTP, or up to $\sim 5.5\ \mu\text{m}$ for LiNbO_3 [23], [24], [25].

In order to develop efficient frequency converters into wavelengths longer than $5\ \mu\text{m}$, non-oxide crystals should be employed because of their wider transparency range up to $\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$ in some cases. Generally, sulphide-, selenide-, or phosphide-based crystals can be used and huge effort has been made to fabricate and investigate such crystals having acceptably high effective nonlinear optical coefficient ($>5\ \text{pm/V}$) and reasonably high optical damage threshold [18]. Quasi-phase-matched (QPM), orientation-patterned (OP) semiconductors as OP-GaAs present other interesting possibilities; nevertheless, dimensions of such structures are limited by the fabrication process.

Moreover, because of two-photon absorption at $\sim 1\ \mu\text{m}$, materials such as GaAs or GaSe have to be usually driven at $>1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ presenting a limiting factor for available pumping sources [26], [27]. A similar situation in terms of available pumping sources applies for crystalline ZnGeP_2 (ZGP) also.

Concerning more closely on DFG systems excited by pulses at the wavelength of $\sim 1\ \mu\text{m}$, many works were devoted to nanosecond pumping. For example, 10-ns pulses with the peak power of 3 kW at $7.9\ \mu\text{m}$ were generated using a BaGa_4Se_7 (BGSe) crystal [28]. In order to achieve orders of magnitude higher peak power, excitation by shorter pulses in a picosecond range can be used.

Several other works concerning this approach based on the BGSe crystals were published. Using this crystal driven by

a 30 ps Nd:YAG laser, output energy of 140–230 μJ at 8–14 μm with the peak power of up to $\sim 7\ \text{MW}$ has been achieved [29]. Moreover, the highest peak power of $\sim 27\ \text{MW}$ at $3.9\ \mu\text{m}$ (energy of 830 μJ in 30 ps pulses) was generated under similar pumping conditions [30]. Using LiInS_2 (LIS) crystal driven by a 25 ps Nd:YAG laser, output energy of 350 μJ at $5.4\ \mu\text{m}$ corresponding to the peak power of up to $\sim 14\ \text{MW}$ has been demonstrated [2]. Our group has also presented preliminary results on BGSe under 1.8 ps pumping in [31]. Using LiGaS_2 and LiGaSe_2 crystals it was possible to generate up to 50 μJ energy level in the 4.6–10.8 μm wavelength range with the peak power of up to $\sim 2.5\ \text{MW}$ under pumping by a $1.064\ \mu\text{m}$, 20 ps Nd:YAG laser [32].

There is also a growing number of works devoted to intra-pulse difference frequency generation (iDFG) in a timescale of tens of femtoseconds [33], [34], [35], [36], [37]. This method is generally versatile, simple, and robust. On the other hand, generated mid-IR pulse energy is comparatively low. In order to generate such pulses at $\sim \mu\text{J}$ energy level, it is useful to incorporate amplifier stages. For example, a developed system extended by two OPA stages based on LiGaS_2 enabling to generate 6 μJ , $\sim 100\ \text{fs}$ pulses at $\sim 6\ \mu\text{m}$ was demonstrated [34].

We have developed a system generating between these two temporal ranges, i.e. pulses in a picosecond scale. Mid-IR pulses with the energy up to 130 μJ corresponding to the peak power of $\sim 72\ \text{MW}$ were generated. Using various nonlinear crystals, tunability in the wavelength range from 5 up to 13 μm was achieved. Comparative study of AgGaS_2 (AGS), BaGa_4Se_7 (BGSe), LiGaS_2 (LGS), or LiGaSe_2 (LGSe) with various lengths was performed. The developed DFG system was driven by the $1.03\ \mu\text{m}$, 1.8 ps, Yb:YAG thin-disk based Perla B laser system at the HiLASE centre [24].

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The fundamental optical layout of the designed DFG system is presented in Fig. 1. The principal idea of this setup was proposed in [38]. Additional lenses were used in the setup in order to optimize beam spot size on the SHG, OPG, and DFG elements.

Notation in the order of pump – signal – idler ($\lambda_{\text{pump}} < \lambda_{\text{signal}} < \lambda_{\text{idler}}$) will be used in the following descriptions of three-wave mixing processes. The $1.03\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ laser with maximum pulse energy of 11 mJ was used as a pump source for a double-stage frequency-converter into the mid-IR region. According to the autocorrelation measurement, the pulse duration was 1.8 ps assuming sech^2 pulse shape. The spectral bandwidth was $\sim 1.5\ \text{nm}$ indicating that the pulse was not fully transform-limited.

The laser output energy was adjustable using a motorized attenuator and the pulse repetition rate was reduced from 1 kHz down to 10 Hz by a pulse picker during most of the experiments. Furthermore, the setup with the 8 mm long BGSe crystal was tested at the highest output energy at the pump repetition rate of 100 Hz without any damage nor DFG output characteristics decrease. This result confirms that further mean output power scaling is possible.

The first stage was a generator of a signal wave for DFG based on a double pass optical parametric generator - amplifier (OPG - OPA) system driven by a second harmonic

Fig. 1. Optical layout of the DFG system in collinear geometry. SHG: second harmonic generator, OPG: optical parametric generator, DFG: difference frequency generator. TFP: Thin film polarizer; HWP: half-wave plate @ 1030 nm; M1, M2, M3: HR @ 1030 nm; M4: HR @ 515 nm; M5 and M6: HR @ 1100-1300 nm. DM: dichroic mirrors: DM1: HR @ 515 nm, HT @ 1030 nm; DM2 and DM3: HR @ 515 nm, HT @ 1100-1300 nm; DM4: HR @ 1120-1270 nm, HT @ 1030 nm. Ge: Germanium plate used to block pump as well as signal radiation. Insets: spatial profiles of pump and signal beams. Additional lenses used for optimization of the beam spot sizes are not shown for better clarity.

generation (SHG) stage. Generated idler wave (tunable in a range of ~ 1.12 to $1.30 \mu\text{m}$) was used as a signal wave for the DFG stage. DFG was studied in several nonlinear crystals described in section III. The horizontally polarized pump beam ($1.03 \mu\text{m}$) and vertically polarized signal beam (~ 1.12 to $1.30 \mu\text{m}$) were combined in the type II DFG crystal. A delay stage formed by the mirrors M1-M2 was used in the pump beam for precise adjustment of the temporal overlap between the pump and signal beam. The HWP2 was used to adjust the correct polarization of the pump wave for DFG.

Details of the first stage of the frequency conversion system are following: The SHG was based on an LBO crystal with a length of 5 mm, aperture of $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$, cut at $\Theta = 90^\circ$, $\phi = 13^\circ$, anti-reflection-coated (AR) at 515 nm and 1030 nm. During the DFG measurements described later, HWP1 was used to keep excitation pulse energy for the SHG crystal at a constant level of 2.2 mJ. This value was limited by the damage threshold under given conditions. Therefore, signal pulse energy for DFG was also kept at a constant level while pump pulse energy for DFG was varied during these measurements. Residual $1.03 \mu\text{m}$ radiation was transmitted through DM1 into a beam dump. SHG radiation at 515 nm served as excitation for the OPG-OPA system. It was based on a KTP crystal with a length of 5 mm, aperture of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$, cut at $\Theta = 73^\circ$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, AR at 900–1400 nm, for $o \rightarrow eo$ interaction (pump \rightarrow signal, idler). During the first pass through the KTP, a spectrally-broadband ($>30 \text{ nm}$) and spatially-divergent conical idler beam was generated. It was transmitted through DM3 and reflected back into the KTP by M5. The pump beam at 515 nm was reflected by DM3 and further reflected back into the KTP by M4. M4 was placed on a precise translation stage in order to adjust the temporal overlap between the pump and idler beams in the KTP during the second pass. The path of the back-reflected pump

at 515 nm was slightly misaligned in the horizontal plane by M4 and therefore the back-reflected pump can be blocked by an iris placed in front of the SHG crystal. Using this second pass, the idler beam was amplified as well as spectrally and spatially narrowed. This idler beam was further transmitted through DM2 and directed into the DFG crystal. The idler wave generated by this OPG-OPA system was tunable in the wavelength range of 1.12 to $1.30 \mu\text{m}$ by slight rotation of the KTP crystal. The spectral full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) was 10 nm and the maximum generated energy of $\sim 25 \mu\text{J}$ was limited by the KTP damage threshold. The spatial profile is presented in the inset of Fig. 1. It has to be noted that there was also a shorter (signal) wave generated around $0.93 \mu\text{m}$ also but it was not used for further experiments and it was transmitted through DM4.

Nonlinear crystals used in the second stage of the frequency conversion are described in section III in detail. The pump beam spatial profile was approximately Gaussian with an average diameter of 2.8 mm (measured at $1/e^2$) in the place of the DFG crystal. The calculated effective area of 3.1 mm^2 was used for further energy density calculations in accordance with the ISO standard 21254-1. A smaller pump beam may lead to higher conversion efficiencies at lower pump energies, but the main objective of this work was to use the maximum available pumping energy and generate as high mid-IR energy as possible without the DFG crystal damage. The signal beam diameter in the place of the DFG crystal was about 1.6 mm.

III. NONLINEAR CRYSTALS FOR MID-IR DIFFERENCE FREQUENCY GENERATION

DFG was investigated in nonlinear crystals of AGS, BGSe, LGS, and LGSe. Overview of all investigated samples is presented in Table I together with fundamental crystallographic

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF THE INVESTIGATED DFG CRYSTAL SAMPLES

	AGS	BGSe			LGSe			LGS		
Anisotropy	neg. uniax.	biaxial			biaxial			biaxial		
Class	42m	m			mm2			mm2		
DFG interaction type	1	1			2			2		
Pump-Signal-Idler	eo0	oee			eoe			eoe		
Principal plane	-	XZ			XY			XY		
$\Theta; \varphi$	34°; 45°	45°; 0°			90°; 34°			90°; 39°		
d_{eff} , pm/V	10.5	27			9.2			5.6		
Length, mm	2	1	4	8	2	4	8	2	4	8
Aperture, mm ²	8×5	4×4	5×5	5×6	4×4	4×4	4×4	5×5	4×4	4×4
AR coating	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no

Fig. 2. Calculated phase-matching curves of AGS, BGSe, LGS, and LGSe crystals for collinear setup in principal planes according to Table I.

properties. Length of the samples was in the range between 1 and 8 mm. Some of the crystals were anti-reflection (AR) coated at 1.2-1.5 μm . Nonlinear characteristics of the crystals were calculated using SNLO [25]. The crystals were cut at the angles (Θ , ϕ) enabling access to a reasonably high effective nonlinear optical coefficient d_{eff} for the selected type of interaction at the following central wavelengths: pump 1.03 μm , signal 1.20 μm , idler 7.27 μm . It has to be noted that magnitudes of nonlinear optical coefficients used in SNLO for BGSe are somewhat uncertain and several papers presenting novel data were published recently [39], [40]. On the other hand, values of d_{eff} for AGS, LGS, and LGSe have been validated with the same results in many publications. Phase-matching curves are presented in Fig. 2.

Unpolarized transmission spectra of these crystals were measured using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-3600) and an FT-IR spectrometer (Nicolet). Fresnel reflections were subtracted, spectral dependencies of the net absorption coefficient were calculated and they are presented in Fig. 3. Slight noise at ~ 4.3 μm is essentially caused by CO_2 absorption and noise around 6.4 μm is caused by water vapor absorption. These data are in a good agreement with SNLO [25]. It can be seen that the absorption coefficient increases significantly (higher than

Fig. 3. Spectral dependencies of net absorption coefficients for AGS, BGSe, LGS, and LGSe.

2 cm^{-1}) above ~ 9.0 μm for LGS, above ~ 10.6 μm for LGSe, above ~ 11.9 μm for AGS, and above ~ 17 μm for BGSe.

IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF MID-IR DIFFERENCE FREQUENCY GENERATION

Laser-induced damage threshold (LIDT) was measured using same pump laser system but slightly different beam spot sizes in some cases. Input surface damage was observed at pump pulse energy densities of approximately 0.16 and 0.21 J/cm^2 for the AR-coated BGSe and LGSe crystals, respectively. In order not to damage other crystals, the energy density was kept slightly lower during the following DFG measurements. Although these measured values are not fully comparable with the values published for the uncoated crystals, they present a good estimation for further measurements. The uncoated AGS and LGS crystals were not damaged by the pump energy density of 0.15 and 0.23 J/cm^2 , respectively.

Mid-IR single pulse energy generated by the DFG system operated at 10 Hz was measured by a sensitive energy probe (Coherent J10MB-LE). When the system was operated at 100 Hz, the single pulse energy was measured by the energy probe and also mean power was measured by a power meter (Thorlabs

Fig. 4. Mid-IR $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ output energy (left) and conversion efficiency (right) achieved with 8 mm long DFG crystals (top row), 4 mm long DFG crystals (middle row), and 1 or 2 mm long DFG crystals (bottom row). Points: measured data; line: numerical modeling.

PM16-401). The single pulse energy was calculated from this power measurement and the values are in good agreement.

Characteristics of generated pulse energy and energy conversion efficiency of the output radiation at the wavelength of $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ as a function of the pump pulse energy for all investigated

crystals are presented in Fig. 4. This wavelength was chosen because of the crystals cut as well as limited LGS transmission range. Germanium filter transmittance was taken into account, i.e. the presented values are in front of this filter. All crystals were tested up to the pump energy density close to the limit given by

Fig. 5. DFG spectral tunability using the BGSe crystal (left) and LGS crystal (right) at high pump energy.

the LIDT value. It has to be also noted that the 8 mm long LGS crystal was partially damaged during previous experiments that might negatively affect the output energy. The highest output energy of 130 μJ with the conversion efficiency of 2% was achieved using the 8 mm long LGS crystal for the pump energy of 6.7 mJ corresponding to energy density of almost 0.2 J/cm^2 . Assuming the output pulse duration comparable to the pump pulse duration of 1.8 ps, the peak power exceeded 72 MW level. It has to be noted that for the highest pump level, the optimal signal energy might be higher, but it was limited by the OPG/OPA performance. Maximum conversion efficiency for this crystal was 2.5% at lower pump energy of 3 mJ. Using the 8 mm long BGSe crystal, the highest output energy was 120 μJ for pump energy of 5.1 mJ with the conversion efficiency of 2.3%. It should be also noted that at low pump energy of 1 mJ, the output energy was about 50 μJ and the conversion efficiency reached 5%. Using the 8 mm long LGS crystal, the highest output energy was 60 μJ with the conversion efficiency of 1.4%. Using shorter crystals, the output energies were generally lower. In the case of 4 mm long crystals, the maximum output energy was $\sim 100 \mu\text{J}$ for the LGS and LGS crystals, and $\sim 60 \mu\text{J}$ for the BGSe crystal. The conversion efficiencies were up to 2.5% in the case of LGS crystal for pump energy of 2.5 mJ. In the case of 1 or 2 mm long crystals, the maximum output energy was 45 μJ for the 2 mm long LGS crystal. Using the 2 mm long LGS, 2 mm long AGS, and 1 mm long BGSe crystals, the maximum output energy was comparable at a level of 25 μJ . The maximum conversion efficiency was 1% for the 2 mm long LGS crystal. Shot-to-shot energy stability at high pump energy level was less than $\pm 5\%$.

Presence of energy roll-off effect was observed for longer crystals or crystals with higher nonlinear coefficients. This phenomenon is probably given by re-conversion of the idler wave back into the pump and signal waves. Solid lines in the graphs present results of numerical modeling based on SNLO [25] taking into account the spatial distribution with diffractive effects. It has to be noted that a shorter interaction length was used in this numerical modeling, taking into account non-optimal spatial or

temporal overlap of the pump and signal beams. According to the simulation, in the ideal case for the 8 mm long crystals, the maximum output energy would be about 2 times higher.

The generated spectra in the mid-IR region were measured using a single grating monochromator (Oriol model 77250 with 77302 grating covering the spectral range 4–16 μm , 75 lines/mm) together with a cryogenically-cooled mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) photodetector (Judson-Teledyne J15D12, spectral range 3–13 μm). Spectral resolution was on the order of 30 nm. The signal wave at the desired wavelength for DFG was tuned by the KTP crystal rotation, and the DFG crystal was rotated correspondingly in order to match the phase-matching condition.

Examples of the spectra generated by DFG using the 8 mm long BGSe and LGS crystals are presented in Fig. 5. In the case of the BGSe crystal, tunability in the range from ~ 6.5 to 13 μm was achieved. Shorter wavelengths might possibly be generated, but effort has been made to investigate a long-wavelength spectral part. The spectral width (FWHM) ranged from 80 cm^{-1} at $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ to 40 cm^{-1} at $\sim 12.7 \mu\text{m}$. It has to be noted that it was not possible to measure longer wavelengths than $\sim 13 \mu\text{m}$ because of the MCT photodetector sensitivity limit. Using the 8 mm LGS crystal, the overall tunability range was ~ 5.3 to 8.3 μm and the long-wavelength part was probably limited by the crystal transmittance. The spectral width was ranging from 70 cm^{-1} at $\sim 5.5 \mu\text{m}$ to 80 cm^{-1} at $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A comparative study of nonlinear crystals for picosecond difference frequency generation in the mid-IR was presented. Crystals of AgGaS_2 , BaGa_4Se_7 , LiGaSe_2 , and LiGaS_2 with various lengths were used. The developed tunable DFG system was driven by the 1.03 μm , 1.8 ps, Yb:YAG thin-disk laser system operated at a repetition rate of 10 or 100 Hz. Picosecond mid-IR pulses at a wavelength of $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ with energy up to 130 μJ corresponding to the peak power of $\sim 72 \text{ MW}$ were generated using the 8 mm long LiGaS_2 crystal. Using

various nonlinear crystals, DFG tunability in the wavelength range from ~ 6 up to $13 \mu\text{m}$ was achieved. In agreement with simulation results, higher conversion efficiency up to 5% can be achieved for low pump energy densities using crystals with higher d_{eff} (BGSe or LGSe). On the other hand, at high pump energy densities approaching the crystal damage threshold, the conversion efficiency of 1 to 2% is comparable for all crystals due to strong reconversion. Longer crystals (4 or 8 mm) are beneficial for higher achievable maximum generated energy for the investigated pump pulse duration.

Yb:YAG thin-disk pump laser allows further increase of the output pulse repetition rate up to 1 kHz and therefore average output power scalability of the whole DFG system.

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